

Research Article

Treatment of Patients with Valvular Pulmonary Stenosis Congenitally by Balloon Pulmonary Valvuloplasty

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE: The aim of this study was to know the results in Pakistani adults immediately after balloon valvuloplasty with no complications and pulmonary valve stenosis occurs congenitally. Balloon valvuloplasty is the 1st line treatment for pulmonary stenosis congenitally in a pediatric population.

METHODS: The Hospital registry retrospective searches of all patients who underwent pulmonary balloon valvuloplasty between 2016 and 2017 were performed with demographic and hemodynamic echocardiographic findings, followed by procedure and hemodynamic data.

RESULTS: Thirty-one patients (10 males and 21 females) underwent balloon lung valvuloplasty from 2016 to 2017; the mean age was 25.65 ± 7.24 years and the distribution was 16-47 years. In all patients single balloon procedure was used. The right ventricular systolic pressure was 115.8 ± 48.5 mm Hg, systolic pressure gradient was 74.8 ± 33.4 mm Hg, peak and the pulmonary valve peak was 142.1 ± 47.9 . For the 3503 ($p = 0.001$), 6.7 and 24.5 ± 11.4 mmHg $\pm$ systolic pulmonary artery were not significantly changed. All patients showed improvement symptomatically and no significant mortality or complication was observed.

CONCLUSION: Valvuloplasty is the effective and reliable treatment for valvular stenosis occurs congenitally in adult patients.

KEYWORDS: Balloon valvuloplasty, pulmonary stenosis, adult.

INTRODUCTION

Stenosis of Pulmonary valve (PS in short) is in most cases congenital and approximately 6 to 11% of all congenital defects of heart. The extensive number of patients have a dome or conical like pulmonary valve and thick because of compression fusion. Sometimes, displacement of valve is noted associated with Noonan syndrome. The severity of pulmonary stenosis is classified in different forms; The most commonly used system is the systolic pressure gradient defined as four degrees of transverse displacement: <PG 25

mmHg - insignificant; PG, 26 to 50 mmHg: light; PG 51 to 80 mmHg - medium; PG and "81 mmHg-Severo2 History Naturally reveal that Pulmonary Stenosis has a poor prognosis relatively in the long run, particularly right heart failure, associated with a short left to right due to severe congenital valvular heart disease (Class I percutaneous intervention includes: asymptomatic patients with pulmonary valve Figure 60mm Hg or higher mean Doppler 40mmHg pulmonary insufficiency is greater than

a maximum maximum instant Doppler gradient arched medium. means pulmonary valve dome and 30 mmHg, provided there is less pulmonary insufficiency than the middle of symptomatic patients with a maximum instantaneous Doppler gradient exceeding 50 mm Hg or higher Doppler. Surgical valvotomy has been adopted for a critical valvulopathy Since 1947.

Semb et al In 1979. Figure 5 is a non-operative figure of a pulmonary valve dilatation using a technique of balloon valvoplasty in a first pediatric patient and then in 1982; Pepin et al. In an adult patient 6, he successfully described lung balloon valvuloplasty (BPV) for the first time.

In the last 30 years, both non-surgical and long-term advantages of this non-invasive procedure for infants and children are well known.

However, same data are relatively rare in adults, especially elderly patients.12-15 Here, in adult patients with pulmonary valve stent- valvuloplasty experience.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Study was conducted at the Institute of Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. Between 2009 and 2012, patients who underwent transthoracic echocardiographic percutaneous balloon pulmonary valvuloplasty (PBV) retrospectively noted hospital records, especially the pulmonary valve stenosis, both Grampositive and cardiac catheterization data (on the right side where intracardiac pressures were obtained) both the previous procedure and the subsequent procedure. The procedure was performed on strict aseptic conditions for the right femoral vena cava PBV. Right ventricular angiography (RV) was recorded using a catheter drill, taken at a lateral position with hemodynamic data, including a braid catheter and RV pressure and PA pressure. External rigid, change length Amplatzter guide cables were used. A single balloon technique (Fig. 1) was used for all patients with a size of 1.3 mm along the diameter of the pulmonary ring solid.

Figure 1, single balloon pulmonary valvuloplasty

In most cases balloon dilatation is repeated (2-3 times) and extinguishing is carried out at all times, and Deflation is performed in 30 seconds, with a minimum time interval of 3-5 minutes It was not much. After balloon dilatation, hemodynamic data were checked again. The patients were discharged the next day and followed OPD follow-up 8-12 weeks later Shown in (Fig.2)

Fig 2: Types of Baloons Used

of the opening of valve orifice.

After BPV, right ventricle systolic pressure (RVSP) decreased from 142.2 ± 47.9 to 74.7 ± 33.4 mmHg and pulmonary valve peak to peak systolic pressure gradient decreased from 115.7 ± 48.5 to 40.5 ± 33.9 mmHg. There was also a significant rise in pulmonary artery systolic pressure from 24.6 ± 6.7 to 35.03 ± 11.4 mmHg ($p= 0.001$), Table 2.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data was entered in SPSS 16.0 version for Windows. Categorical variables were expressed as gender, frequency and percentage, and continuous variables such as age and intracardiac pressure were taken as $\pm$ SD (standard deviation) mean. To

compare data differences Paired Student's t test was used and p-value 0.05 was taken significant.

Table 1 : Individual Parameters Of Study Population

Sr#	Age (years)	Sex	Pre.RVP (mmHg)	Post.RVP (mmHg)	Pre.PAP (mmHg)	Post.PAP (mmHg)	Balloon Type
1	16	F	113	40	22	27	Cordis
2	17	F	106	58	21	31	Cordis
3	20	F	114	55	26	43	Tyshak II
4	23	F	216	85	21	30	Cordis
5	27	F	72	40	30	30	Numed
6	25	F	180	117	25	26	Cordis
7	30	F	62	36	20	29	Zemedill
8	35	F	166	100	20	36	Tyshak II
9	20	F	114	55	26	36	Tyshak II
10	25	F	190	95	25	40	Tyshak II
11	25	F	153	98	15	16	Cordis
12	19	F	133	60	27	45	Cordis
13	40	F	266	100	25	40	Cordis
14	24	F	150	100	24	40	Cordis
15	19	F	98	46	24	26	Cordis
16	30	F	124	44	33	35	Cordis
17	22	F	129	47	21	22	Cordis
18	18	F	155	69	24	35	Cordis
19	47	F	121	75	32	44	Cordis
20	35	F	153	100	18	28	Cordis
21	40	F	266	100	25	40	Cordis
22	24	M	128	60	19	30	Numed
23	24	M	139	79	29	59	Cordis
24	21	M	132	119	18	19	Cordis Marc
25	21	M	90	40	18	21	Cordis
26	25	M	167	75	50	72	Numed
27	26	M	161	56	22	30	Tyshak II
28	24	M	92	40	21	35	Z-Med
29	28	M	151	95	37	50	Z-Med
30	25	M	92	43	21	37	Cordis
31	20	M	173	71	22	34	Cordis

RVP=Right ventricular pressure, PAP= Pulmonary artery pressure, M= Male, F= Female

RESULTS

The Working population ranged from 16 to 47 years and mean age ranged from 25.65 ± 7.24 years was taken during the year 2016 to 2017, and BPV was performed in 31 patients (10 males and 21 females) with congenital valve PS were treated. Transthoracic echocardiography showed that all patients had isolated congenital pulmonary valve stasis without congenital heart disease (AP) in another structural heart-related disease. angiogram to enhance the main pulmonary artery and demonstrate ventricular post-stenotic VD in pulmonary valves of trabecular dome in all patients. None of the patients had a displaced valve or organic infundibular stenosis; however, reactive infundibular stenosis was observed (diastolic dilatation on angiography). Later to BPV, the transvalvular flow expands due to the way open of the valve hole. After VPP, the systolic right ventricular pressure (RVSP) decreased 142.2 ± 47.9 , the peak difference at the pulmonary valve peak decreased from $115.7 \pm$

48.5 to 33.9 ± 40.5 mm Hg at 74.7 ± 33.4 mmHg. 35.03 ± 11.4 mm Hg ($p = 0.001$), an increase of 6.24 ± 6.7 in the systolic pulmonary artery of Table 2. All patients showed symptomatic improvement (NYHA class III and NYHA class I-II). Transient hypotension was observed with SBP <100 mmHg and bradyarrhythmia in three cases with spontaneous resolution. There were no critical complications like tamponade, severe pulmonary regurgitation (PR) or mortality. None of our patients had post-care procedures in the ICU / CCU and were discharged within 24 hours of the next day.

DISCUSSION

Our findings suggest that BPV is a effective and safe method in adult patients with Pulmonary Stenosis and congenital valvular disease. BPV has been the preferred treatment for the first major valve electrode reported in 1982, and surgical valvulotomy has been performed in pediatric patients. The double balloon procedure was first described by Al-Kasab et al. The 2 balloons use technique even during full dilation may allow less blood flow between them and may lead to less changes hemodynamically. Inoue Balloon is also used for this purpose and has the advantage that it can be adjusted according to its size, which allows for gradual expansion. At the same time, the infundibulum of the RV or the main PA causes the least possible damage due to short, self-positioned characters. However, Inoue's balloon has disadvantages including a large capsule, harsh features and high cost. For this reason, the double ball technique is now preferred. In last studies, determinants independent of long-term outcomes after PPV in pediatric patients are due to morphologically valvular balloon ring diameter ratio, and sudden pressure gradient after gradual dilatation of the lungs. If the valve is displaced, a bad prognosis is observed if the relationship between the balloon diameter <1.2 or valve valve > 36 mmHg residual pressure is longer. Some writers have stated that adults have no need to use a larger size balloon (1.2 to 0.5 diameter) in children, because of lower restenosis rate in

adults (4.8%) than children which is 18%).) and no relationship clearly between hemodynamic results and ball size occurs. Most of the researches suggest that if the residual BP is not greater than 36 mm Hg, the ratio of balloon-ring should not increase by 1.5 because of increase in PR or annular lacerations. Literature review suggests that RP in most studies is higher after BPV surgery.

Table 2: Mean RVP and Mean PAP Pre & Post Procedure

	Pre-Procedure	Post-Procedure	P-Value
Mean RV Pressure (mmHg)	142.16 ± 47.93	74.77 ± 33.39	0.001
Mean PA Pressure (mmHg)	24.55 ± 6.74	35.03 ± 11.44	0.001

RVP=Right ventricular pressure; PAP= Pulmonary artery pressure

The prevalence of new PR is 14-39%, but most of the cases are intermediate. PR with BPV, surgical valvulotomy is about 60% lower. Major complications of BPV have been reported in pediatric patients, cardiac perforation (0.1%) and including death (0.2%). In adult patients, Hermann et al. Kaul et al. 1 death and 1 cardiac tamponade. Surgical valvotomy in contrast, has a 1.5% to 2% mortality rate. We have not found such complications in our series. Only transient arrhythmia and mild hypotension were observed during the procedure. All patients were well tolerated with good results. According to previous studies, the decrease in RV systolic pressure after valvuloplasty has changed from 40% to 72% and the decrease in pressure gradient in transvalvular varied from 46% to 94%. Our results are comparable to these findings: a 57-77% reduction in RV pressure and reduction in transvalvular pressure gradient in average is 34%. Infundibular stenosis significantly is a hurdle that can lead to a high residual pressure gradient after PPV. Experts have suggested performing a myometectomy if the postoperative pressure of RV is greater than 100 mm Hg or if the pressure gradient is greater than 80 mm Hg. Recovery and shrinkage recovery in the tachycardia cause an increase in heart rate, but at the same time the RV

reduces the clogging of the exit flow and increases the pressure gradient. Infundibular spasms after BPV have been reported by Al-Kasab et al. We have not found this problem. In addition, infundibular hypertrophy of secondary RV to PS is gradually withdrawn after PPV and this regression may be accelerated by the administration of oral beta-blockers. For this reason, a continuous improvement in the transvalvular pressure gradient is usually obtained.

CONCLUSION

BPV is a safe and effective treatment for adult patients with congenital pulmonary valve stenosis.

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